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Modeling and Optimization of a Hybrid Energy System Incorporating Wave, Offshore Wind, and Solar for Oahu, Hawaii

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Abstract

Hawaii, as an isolated island state, heavily relies on imported fossil fuels, resulting in higher electricity prices compared to mainland states. The transportation sector alone consumes nearly 45% of the total imported fuel. To overcome this challenge and transition to a sustainable energy system, Hawaii aims for 70% renewable energy by 2030 and 100% renewables by 2045. As technology progresses, the transportation sector may eventually shift towards a hydrogen fuel-based fleet for long-distance trucking. Current hydrogen production, however, is mainly derived from fossil fuels, thus there is a need for expanding green hydrogen production. The state's limited land availability and high land values make scaling up land-based renewable energy projects difficult. However, the state can tap into the potential of offshore wind, solar, and wave energy. This study explores the synergy between these renewable resources and hydrogen production to develop a hybrid energy system optimized for Oahu Island, aiming to minimize costs while achieving Hawaii's decarbonization and clean energy goals. This paper introduces a capacity sizing optimization method and employs the NREL HOPP tool for hydrogen production analysis and cost assessment for a location in Oahu, Hawaii.

Keywords: Hybrid Energy System; NREL HOPP; Hawaii O'hau; Wave; Offshore Hydrogen

1. Introduction

The island state of Hawaii encounters significant challenges due to its remote location and limited access to fossil fuel reserves, which results in a substantial reliance on petroleum imports. This heavy dependence on imported petroleum has led to Hawaii having the highest energy costs among all states. As of March 2023, the cost of electricity energy in Hawaii (\$/kWh) is nearly three times higher than the average electricity cost paid by customers in the U.S [1].

The estimated energy consumption for Hawaii is as shown in Fig. 1 (a). In 2021, the transportation sector emerged as the largest energy consumer, accounting for 53% of the total energy consumption. This sector encompasses various modes of transportation, including cars, buses, trucks, and planes, highlighting the significance of addressing energy efficiency and alternative fuel options in the state's transportation infrastructure. The industrial sector accounted for 18% of the energy consumption, playing a vital role in Hawaii's economy. The commercial sector followed closely behind, representing 15% of the total energy consumption. Lastly, the residential sector accounts 14% of the energy

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consumption in 2021. The electricity sector on the other hand generated 77.2% of total generation from fossil fuel-based energy resources and the statistics is as shown in Fig. 1 (b) [2].

Fig. 1. (a) Hawaii Energy Consumption Estimates (2021) [1]; (b) Hawaii Net Electricity Generation by Source (2021) [2].

In recent years, the transportation and electricity sectors have rapidly shifted towards clean energy solutions, particularly electric vehicles (EVs) and upcoming hydrogen trucks [3]. Hawaii, aiming to achieve substantial renewable energy targets, plans to generate 70% of its energy from renewable sources by 2030 and achieve 100% renewable energy by 2045 [1]. To attain these goals, understanding and addressing energy consumption patterns in these sectors is vital. By investing in renewable energy sources, implementing energy-saving technologies, and promoting responsible energy use, the state can progress towards a greener, more energy-efficient future.

Challenges arise in Hawaii due to limited land availability and high land values, particularly for land-based renewable energy projects like wind and solar arrays. However, Hawaii's abundant natural resources and favorable geographical location make offshore floating wind, floating solar, and wave energy promising alternatives for meeting energy needs. Integrating these resources with energy storage systems such as large-scale batteries or hydrogen storage can ensure stable electricity transmission, reduce reliance on imported fuels, and provide clean energy for ground fleet vehicles.

Presently, the United States (US) produces 10 million metric tons of hydrogen annually, primarily through fossil fuel and natural gas reforming processes [4]. The primary use of hydrogen can be observed in the oil refining and ammonia industries, but its application can be observed in various sectors including the industry, where hydrogen and hydrogen compounds are used for processing, refining and reducing agents. Hydrogen can also be used in transportation, energy storage and power generation. The well-known practices currently for hydrogen production includes steam methane reforming for fossil fuel-based resources and electrolysis for renewable energy.

This study focuses on Oahu, the most extensive and densely populated island in Hawaii, with an aim to assess the feasibility of fulfilling 25% of the island's peak power demand with offshore renewable energy and green hydrogen, equivalent to 275 megawatts (MW) (Oahu's 2021 peak load was 1,100 MW [5]). The analysis centers on using offshore hybrid systems that include wave, wind, and solar farms, along with hydrogen production for transportation. The study evaluates the minimum capacity required for this hybrid system during farm planning. The generated power will be employed for hydrogen production. The remainder of this paper is as follows; Section 2 discusses the methodology for hybrid plant design and economic analysis, including resource assessment, device specifications, and systems integration, and assumptions used for analysis. Section 3 presents the analysis results and Section 4 discusses those results and summarizes the main contributions and limitations of the work, and opportunities for future work.

2. Analysis for Offshore Hybrid Energy Systems in Oahu

Hybrid offshore renewable energy systems are integrated energy systems that harness multiple renewable energy sources in offshore environments to produce electricity and other products, like hydrogen. These systems combine different technologies, such as offshore wind power, wave energy, tidal energy, ocean thermal energy and potentially other marine-based renewable sources, as well as energy storage to maximize energy production and enhance overall system performance. By leveraging the diverse energy potential of the ocean, hybrid offshore renewable energy systems aim to overcome the limitations and variability of individual technologies while optimizing power generation, storage, and transmission.

2.1. Offshore renewable energy data

The island of Oahu in Hawaii stands as the most densely inhabited region, boasting abundant natural assets in the form of waves, offshore wind, and solar potential. Presently, the Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM) has identified two sites as prime zones for harnessing floating offshore wind energy within the vicinity of Oahu: the Oahu north call area and Oahu south call area. In this paper, the co-located data for different renewable energy resources were obtained from multiple sources for Oahu north call area. The solar data was obtained from the NSRDB database [6], the wave data was obtained from WaveWatchIII [7] which was then interpolated for hourly data, offshore wind data was obtained from Wind Integration National Toolkit [8] and the electrical load consumption data was obtained directly from the Hawaiian Electric Company, Inc (HECO). All resource and load demand data were queried from July 2018 to May 2019.

2.2. NREL Hybrid Optimization and Performance Platform (HOPP) modelling

In this study, we use the Hybrid Optimization and Performance Platform (HOPP) [9, 10] to model and simulate renewable energy and hydrogen generation and costs associated with the offshore hybrid energy systems. HOPP is an open-source, pre-feasibility design and analysis tool which enables fully coupled hybrid system simulation and representation of varying resource, technology, cost, and policy scenarios. HOPP leverages models across disciplines, including pySAM [11] for wave and solar production, battery storage, and cost modeling, FLORIS [12] for wind energy production modeling, Annual Technology Baseline [13] and Program Records [14] for cost estimation assumptions (where possible), ORBIT [15] for offshore wind balance-of-station costs, ProFAST [16] (for hydrogen system production and cost modeling), as well as custom models. The custom models, which include technology-specific operations like battery dispatch, desalination, electrolyzer stack, and systems integration modeling, are fully detailed in previous studies [17]. Appendix A.1 shows the hybrid system design and optimization process flow using HOPP tool.

3. Oahu Offshore Renewable Energy case study

3.1. Offshore renewable energy resource assessment

To assess the availability of the resources, the power yield of each energy resource was obtained for Oahu north call area by generating data for a floating wind turbine with a capacity of 12 MW, a wave energy converter with a capacity of 1 MW, and offshore solar panels with a total capacity of 10 MW using the HOPP tool. The power curve for offshore floating wind turbine was obtained from FLORIS [12], an example power matrix for wave energy was obtained from a wave energy developer and pySAM model [11] was used for solar.

Fig. 2 Combined Resource Versatility for Offshore solar, wind and wave at Oahu North Call Area.

Further to analyze the impact of individual energy resource, the power profiles for the wave, offshore wind and solar systems were normalized to 1 MW by dividing it by their respective nameplate capacities. The Oahu grid power demand data was also normalized to 1MW by dividing it by its peak value. An analysis was performed to determine which of these renewable energy resources were capable of producing power more than 25% of scaled load demand. Fig. 2 shows the binary results representing the cases where each energy is capable of producing power more than 25% of the scaled load demand. It is to be noted that these results do not represent the combined outputs of each generation type. The results indicate that for 74 hours in a year, no combination of resources was able to produce power greater than the required demand. Wave energy was able to meet the demand for 8189 hours in total and for 1191 hours in the year, wave was the only resource that could generate power greater than the demand. Similarly, wind energy was available for a total of 6556 hours and the wind only resource output was observed for 218 hours

(See Appendix B for more information). These results indicate that the optimal planning of these combined resources can reduce the need for energy storage and provide continuous power.

3.2. Capacity planning and HOPP analysis

The electrical demand data in real-time series for Oahu was gathered concurrently with the wave, offshore wind, and solar resource data, covering identical time spans from July 2018 to May 2019. These datasets were averaged on an hourly basis across different seasons. The objective was to evaluate the most suitable energy type mix and installed capacity when optimizing for lowest installation cost and most consistent continuity of supply (i.e., minimizing periods of zero energy production) by employing the subsequent formulation for mixed integer programming and applying a non-linear optimization.

$$\text{Objective: } \min\{\alpha_1 * \text{installation cost} + \alpha_2 * \text{variation}\} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subjected to: } \text{Energy output from hybrid farm at time } t = \text{Average Load at time } t + \text{variation} \quad (2)$$

Where, α_1 and α_2 are weights. The results of the optimization are as shown in Table 1. The values represent the capacity required for each resource for the given season in Megawatts (MW).

Table 1. Capacity in MW from optimization results.

Season	Offshore wind	Wave	Offshore Solar
Summer	360	15	39
Fall	420	116	22
Winter	468	9	4
Spring	468	326	0
Rounded with contingency	600	400	50

For each generation type, in determining the installed capacity the highest value per season was selected. Considering the variability associated with renewable energy, a contingency value of up to 25%, was considered for calculating the optimal capacity for the hybrid model, which has been determined to stand at a total hybrid plant installed capacity of 1050MW. Within this configuration, the hybrid model has demonstrated its remarkable capability to generate an ample power supply (25% of load demand) for 90.32% of the operational duration. This achievement significantly outshines the wind-only resource, which remained accessible for a lesser span of time, specifically around 68.15% of the total timeframe. This availability can reduce the need for energy storage systems can be reduced to meet the customer demand for electrical power. When solely relying on the wind resource, the capacity factor exhibited a commendable value of 0.62, indicating a respectable utilization of available potential. However, the combined capacity factor for the entire plant, given the optimization for continuity of supply, is approximately 0.41. This shift signifies a purposeful trade-off, where the priority placed on sustainability and the integration of diverse power sources mildly moderates capacity factor to promote a well-rounded and dependable energy mix. Further optimization efforts are planned to increase this capacity factor while maintaining the high availability.

The HOPP scenario was established, considering the comprehensive resource data collected for the Oahu North call area case. Within this framework, the capacities allocated for offshore wind, wave energy, and solar energy were designated as 600 MW, 400 MW, and 50 MW, respectively based on the results from the optimization model. This distribution of resources served as the foundation upon which a case study was constructed, with all energy produced by the hybrid system being used to produce green hydrogen while eliminating the requirement for any additional energy storage systems. The technological specifics for the array cables were chosen to be XLPE 185mm 66kV. The design analysis was executed through the employment of the ORBIT [15] models, recognized for their precision in handling such complex scenarios for wind energy. The array system design considered a semi-submersible design complemented by a semi-taut mooring system. These design elements synergistically ensured stability, resilience, and optimal performance in the face of dynamic oceanic conditions.

The HOPP tool was established with two distinct scenarios that revolve around the location of hydrogen production and the mode of transportation from the ocean to the seashore. In the first scenario, the focal point is on Onshore hydrogen production. This considers placing the electrolyzer and hydrogen storage, boasting a 3-day storage capacity, on the offshore platform. Subsequently, the generated hydrogen is conveyed to the seashore via a pipeline maintained

at a pressure of 10 bar. In contrast, the second scenario considers onshore operations. Here, the emphasis shifts towards having the electrolyzer and hydrogen storage stationed onshore. The transportation of power is facilitated through the utilization of HVDC export cables, meticulously configured at specifications of 2000mm 320kV. This alternative configuration underscores the efficiency and viability of power transmission over considerable distances.

Table 2. HOPP scenario results.

Scenario	Scenario 1			Scenario 2		
	Offshore Wind	Wave + Offshore Wind	Hybrid	Offshore Wind	Wave + Offshore Wind	Hybrid
Plant Capacity (MW)	600	1000	1050	600	1000	1050
Average power (MW/h)	400.8	417.3	429.6	400.8	417.3	429.6
Average hydrogen production (kg/h)	6870.9	7105.4	7303.1	7006.2	7256.5	7448.0
LCOE (\$/MW)	62.4	148.07	145.0	67.23	152.71	149.5
LCOH (\$/kg)	6.4	12.25	12.14	6.42	11.92	11.81
Capacity Factor	0.67	0.42	0.41	0.67	0.42	0.41

Fig. 3. (a) Capital expenditure breakdown Scenario 1; (b) Capital expenditure breakdown Scenario 2.

The outcomes derived from the HOPP analysis for the two considered scenarios have been organized into Table 2. The findings illustrate a noticeable increase in both the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) for the configurations involving wave energy + offshore wind and the hybrid model.

Taking a deeper dive into the breakdown of costs, as depicted in Figure 3, it becomes evident that the cost associated with wave energy devices stands out as a significant factor in both scenarios. This observation underscores the necessity for a strategic reduction in wave energy-related costs to achieve more favorable overall expenses.

Additionally, an examination of the capacity factor reveals interesting insights. The capacities for wave energy and solar energy are recorded as 0.57 and 0.24, respectively. Although the capacity factor for wave energy appears relatively low, the results suggest that wave energy exhibits a remarkable consistency in its power output, which contributes to its reliability as a renewable energy source.

4. Conclusion

Hawaii, an isolated island state, heavily relies on imported fossil fuels resulting in higher energy costs. Looking into the future needs of Hawaii, the need for sustainable and clean energy can be best obtained from offshore resources and combining the offshore wind, wave and solar resources optimally result in minimizing the need for energy storage by providing required power majority of the time. The HOPP analysis of two hydrogen production and transportation scenarios were explored and detailed cost breakdown highlighted the significance of wave energy device costs, emphasizing the need for cost reduction. The capacity factor analysis showed wave energy's consistency despite a lower factor, affirming its reliability as a renewable energy source. It is to be noted that the grid integrated scenario has not been discussed in this paper but will be addressed in the future.

Appendix A. HOPP tool and results

A.1. Hybrid optimization process flow using HOPP tool

A.2. Hybrid optimization LCOH costs and revenue breakdown

Fig. 4. (a) LCOH breakdown Scenario 1; (b) LCOH breakdown Scenario 2.

Appendix B. Resource Assessment

B.1. Resource Versatility for different energy sources

Fig. 5 Resource Versatility for Offshore Wind Energy at Oahu North Call Area.

Fig. 6 Resource Versatility for Wave Energy at Oahu North Call Area.

Fig. 7 Resource Versatility for Offshore Solar Energy at Oahu North Call Area.

Figs. 5 to 7 depict the availability of various energy sources capable of meeting 25% of the total energy demand. These charts display resource availability for each day of the year (x-axis) and each hour of the day (y-axis). The collective representation of these resources is illustrated in Fig. 2. These visualizations serve as valuable tools for understanding and quantifying the availability of a resource, especially when comparing it to other resources, during specific time periods when other resources are not available. This measurement of instant adaptability can be averaged over the entire time frame under consideration to derive the resource versatility metric for a resource.

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